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Linguistic Skills Development of Adults in Learning English as a Foreign Language: Speaking Skill in Ecuadorian Entrepreneurs

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Abstract

This research aims to socialize an educational intervention designed to improve the oral skills of adult entrepreneurs in the province of Manabí, Ecuador. The research is framed in an interpretive paradigm that examines the use of the communicative approach as a method for the acquisition of grammatical content and the implementation of the ECRIF framework to strengthen the communicative competence of entrepreneurs. The post-test was used as the main evaluation instrument, and the results of this study show a significant improvement of 89.23% in the oral skills of the entrepreneurs. It is concluded that through a process of empirical training, integrating theory and practice, the entrepreneurs were able to reach a basic level of content, vocabulary, and grammatical structure through the communicative approach, moreover, the use of the ECRIF framework facilitated the application of this previous knowledge in real-life situations, which contributed in a significant way to the strengthening of speech and oral expression of the entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Andragogy, Communicative Approach, ECRIF Framework, English, Speaking Skill

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship is one of the most supported sectors in Ecuador, because it generates employment opportunities for the population in the Canton Manta is characterized for having an interesting flow of international tourists. The cruises' season begins in September and finishes in May every year, receives about 30 to 40 cruise ships with potential buyers of the products generated by entrepreneurs. Thus, entrepreneurs in the tourism sector, require communication in English language. It is a niche of research that need the attention of local educational institutions.

This research work is linked to two projects of Universidad Laica Eloy Alfaro de Manabí (1) Social transfer of knowledge project "Interdisciplinary project of integral literacy with a focus on gamification for the sustainable development of children, young people and older adults of Manta" and (2) Professional Development of English Teachers in Zone 4 of Ecuador.

Andragogy in English language instruction requires to identify teaching strategies to the tourist development in canton Manta, Ecuador. Ambrose et al., (2010, p.3) define learning as the process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential for improved performance and future learning. As well, learning can see as a cognitive and experiential process through which an individual acquires knowledge, capabilities, understanding or skills in a specific area. It involves integrating new information, changing existing conceptions or enhancing skills through experimentation, instruction, practice or reflection. Robert Slavin (2018) declares learning is the process through which new knowledge, skills, or behaviors are acquired or modified as a result of experience, study, practice, or being taught. It means that learning can occur consciously or unconsciously, in various contexts such as academia, work, social interaction, and daily life. It is a continuous process throughout the human lifespan that can involve the acquisition of academic knowledge, practical skills, values, attitudes, and a deeper understanding of the world around us.

Speaking a language is especially difficult for foreign language learners because effective oral communication requires the ability to use the language appropriately in social interactions. Having in mind that, EFL learners need to have explicit instruction in speaking practice (Shumin, 2002). The research questions to guide this study are:

1. What are the entrepreneurs expectations for the workshop in EFL?
2. What is the previous English language level of the entrepreneurs at the beginning of the workshops?
3. What topics of the educational intervention in English language were the most difficult to learn for the participants?
4. What is the achievement of the participants in English language grammar after part 1 of workshops?
5. What are the changes in entrepreneurs' English language speaking skill after the part 2 of the workshops?

The aim of this research is to transfer the communicative competence in the English language to the entrepreneurs of Manta.

2. Literature Review

In order to facilitate the understanding of this study, the key concepts are presented below.

2.1 Communicative method:

The style of this research acknowledges the communicative approach as the methodology adopted by teachers and applied to achieve meaningful English language learning in second language students. The communicative approach has been considered the most effective theoretical model for developing speaking skill in English language teaching and learning since the early 1970s. Therefore, it is not only important to learn the linguistic forms, but also to understand the potential of the communicative functions and their social significance.

The main objective of the communicative approach to language teaching is to give priority to the development of learners' communicative competence. Communicative competence refers to the ability to use language appropriately and effectively in real-life situations. The communicative approach aims to go beyond traditional language teaching methods that focus solely on grammatical structures and vocabulary in isolation.

The communicative method according to British Council (2015) can be defined as the didactic teaching of how language is successfully acquired through actual communication. Mordaunt et al., (2019) ratify that the communicative method is able to optimize the way language is taught and used, ultimately perfecting a key aspect of language teaching and learning. Thus, when they are exposed to real communication, their brain automatically activates old or previous strategies in a natural way, and they can use the language with the greatest fluency.

It is argued that priority is given to interaction between participants as a strategy for learning a new language (Luque, 2008). In real communication, participants must manage uncertainty about what the other person will say. (Bahrani & Soltani, 2012), and through their contextualized language activities, develop productive (speaking) as well as receptive (listening) skills during dialogue, in any interlocution position in the social setting (Retreage, 2017, p. 1).

Likewise, Rivera-Forty (2021) considers interaction as the main source of communicative exchange between a group of people, since it allows the encoding and decoding of ideas, so that the sender can assimilate the message. Thus, it emphasizes the relevance of communicative strategies, focusing on the role of the interaction process, as stated by Compernelle (2015) where most second and foreign language (L2) teachers know that students must have interaction in the development and improvement of their L2 skills.

Therefore, it is important that they practice the language they are learning and, in particular, that they participate in interactions that take place with other learners inside and outside the classroom (Saeed, 2016). Boonkit (2010) highlights that the incorporation of productive skills (e.g., writing and speaking) are very important for the improvement of practical communicative skills. The development of such skills requires the active participation of the teacher and especially the learners' ability, and meaningful interactions.

Biggs (2003) further suggests that active learners are able to achieve a higher level of engagement and thus a higher level of cognitive learning in their academic work. According to Savignon (1991) receivers and viewers are no longer considered passive participants in learning, they are seen as an active party in the negotiation of meaning. The communicative approach combined the important role of the learners and the active participation they have to manage in order to use the language they learn in real life purpose.

2.2 *Communicative language teaching (CLT)*

To improve this proficiency, we encourage communication and interaction in language learning. Richard and Rogers (2014) state that Communicative Language Teaching is considered more of an approach, as the aims of CLT are to make communicative competence the goal of language teaching and to develop procedures for teaching the four language skills that recognize the interdependence of language and communication. The essence of CLT is the involvement of learners in communication to enable them to develop their communicative competence. Brown (2009) mentions that this approach to language teaching emphasizes communication as the main goal. It focuses on interactive and meaningful language use, using activities to develop learners' real-life communicative skills.

Communicative language teaching can be understood as a set of principles about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn a language, the kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom. (Richards 2005, pag. 2).

Berns (1990,104) provides a useful summary of eight principles of CLT:

1. Language teaching is based on a view of language as communication. That is, Language is seen as a social tool that speakers use to make meaning; speakers communicate about something to someone for some purpose, either orally or in writing.
2. Diversity is recognized and accepted as part of language development and use in second language learners and users, as it is with first language users.
3. A learner's competence is considered in relative, not in absolute, terms.
4. More than one variety of a language is recognized as a viable model for learning and teaching.
5. Culture is recognized as instrumental in shaping speakers' communicative competence, in both their first and subsequent languages.
6. No single methodology or fixed set of techniques is prescribed.
7. Language use is recognized as serving ideational, interpersonal, and textual functions and is related to the development of learners' competence in each.

8. It is essential that learners be engaged in doing things with language—that is, that they use language for a variety of purposes in all phases of learning.

Teachers who are familiar with the principles of communicative language teaching gain a more objective view when planning their lessons, and it is also important because it provides a theoretical basis for designing effective teaching practices. It facilitates a communication-centered approach that promotes language acquisition in a contextual and meaningful way. Also, the CLT develop the communicative competence in second language learners.

2.3. *Encounter, Clarify, Remember, Internalize, Fluency (ECRIF)*

In this study, we focused strongly on using the communicative method with ECRIF framework. Our main aim is to implement an educational intervention to develop speaking skill by implementing the ECRIF framework as a teaching model.

The ECRIF is a framework system of a way of looking at how students learn a language. (Tosuncuoglu, 2017). ECRIF is a framework for understanding learning, looking at how people learn rather than prescribing what teachers should or should not do. By using this framework, educators can understand the intricacies of successful language acquisition. The primary aim of this approach is not to prescribe specific actions, but rather to provide guidance on effective and ineffective practices. It aims to illuminate the ways in which students can optimise their learning experience.

The key to the ECRIF framework is the ***focus on the learning process*** that students go through as they work with the target skill or knowledge rather than what the teacher is doing during the lesson. In this way, the teacher plans activities and thinks about the content to service learning in a principled way ((Kurzweil & Scholl, Understanding Teaching Through Learning, 2005).

ECRIF can be used:

- to plan lessons and adapt course book materials = (*reflecting for action*)
- to assess where students are in their learning process during a lesson = (*reflecting in action*)
- to reflect on student learning after a lesson = (*reflecting on action*)

Caiza (2021) her findings showed that “the learners” speaking skills improved when using ECRIF Framework in the classroom”. Cedeño (2022) states that implementation of ECRIF in the EFL classroom may be a positive first step toward incorporating a framework to guide English language teaching and learning under the principles of CLT which attempts to aid learners to become fluent and effective users of the language.

2.3 *Meaning of each stages in ECRIF*

The ECRIF framework offers a series of strategies that guide learners through the key stages of the process of developing speaking skills, these stages are five in number and each is the foundation for the other (Kurzweil & Scholl, 2005).

E for encounter: The encounter phase of learning is the first time a learner encounters new material or information. It is the introduction to the new language. In the encounter phase, the learner's prior knowledge is activated and what he or she already knows is discovered (Ramadan, 2019).

C for Clarify: Clarifying is something that happens inside the learner when the learner can determine, for example, a certain meaning or pronunciation of a vocabulary word or use a certain grammatical construction in a certain situation. Of course, teachers help to clarify and check or evaluate the learners' understanding of the material. One way teachers check comprehension is with comprehension check questions.

R for remember (controlled practice): This is the first step in memorizing new material. It is usually characterized by repetition, review, and reference to supporting materials through models or instructions.

I for internalize ("learner-initiated" activities): When a learner internalizes material, he or she transfers it to long-term memory. Learners need continued practice to internalize the new language or information. The type of practice here differs from the recall stage in that it will be freer and less controlled. In this stage, learners make more decisions about how to use the information and rely less on external aids.

F for Fluently Use: In this phase of learning, learners use new material and information fluently, according to their current understanding and internalized assimilation of the material. This is the stage where they freely test their internalized knowledge and spontaneously produce the target language creatively in personal and real-life communication tasks.

2.5 *The adults as English learners:*

The theory of andragogy focuses on how adult learners learn. Adults have special needs and requirements as learners (Malik & Khaliq, 2017). Andragogy is a learning process which can help adults to develop ideas and needs. Adult learners can be defined as all people above school age (over 25-30 years old) who wish to learn and acquire a second language in order to grow or develop in different work, academic or social environments. According to Cozma (2015) she defines it as people above the normal age of traditional schooling (more specifically, over 23-25 years old), who freely choose to engage in a particular form of instruction, in order to meet a professional, social or personal need or interest.

According to Knowles (1984) Adult learners are distinguished by 6 main characteristics, those characteristics are: (1) Adult learning is self-directed, (2) Adult learning utilizes knowledge & life experiences, (3) Adult learning is goal-oriented, (4) Adult learning is relevancy-oriented, (5) Adult learning highlights practicality, and (6) Adult learning encourages collaboration. Thus, adult learners tend to be more self-directed, because they are able to direct their own learning over time; enriching their knowledge with day-to-day experiences, they are also ready to take on a new social role, they are in the expectation of learning immediately, adults are generally motivated to learn regardless of internal or external factors.

The previous studies related to this research are, the work of Harmer (2007) affirms that adult learners have developed their cognitive capabilities and conceptual complexity more than the younger learners. Cozma (2015) says that adults are certainly more cooperative learners, and what is more important, their cooperation comes as a natural consequence of their seeing the point of the various instructional situations in which they are involved. The salient feature of these adult learners is that additionally, they are more mature and possess more experience than younger learners, although this could be beneficial as well as problematic. Thus, on the other hand, adult learners have better developed strategies and learning styles that the teacher can help them to take advantage of in their learning. Individual adults learn differently, depending upon their experience, aptitude, and attitude.

3. Methodology

This research is based on the interpretive paradigm, which is a reflection from the practice, where the reality is conformed of observables and external facts, by interpretations and meanings elaborated for the individual, through the interaction with the rest of the people within a determined context. In addition, the nature of this research was exploratory, using a **pre-test, survey, contextual observation, and post-test**. The group of participants is made up of 20 entrepreneurs, including people of human mobility and Ecuadorians, all the members of the group are adults, the ages are between 18 and 74 years old. The 85% are female and 15% are male. These people are entrepreneurs from the city of Manta-Ecuador, who work in the tourism sector promoting and selling their own products. It is important to note that each entrepreneur has a unique product, which means that the entrepreneurship differ from one another.

3.1. Instruments:

The techniques and instruments for the collection of data were:

English language previous knowledge Pre-Test, which was made based on the topics of A1 level according to Cambridge. It consists in 15 questions that are divided in grammar, vocabulary, and speaking. This test evaluates the previous knowledge of the participants, and it measures if the entrepreneurs can dominate the most basic topics of A1 English level. This instrument was examined and approved by 3 professors of the program pedagogy of national and foreign languages affiliated to the university Laica Eloy Alfaro de Manabí.

Survey questionnaire: The aim of this survey is to know the positions and points of view of the entrepreneurs about the English workshop. It consisted of 10 questions about the expectations of the participants concerning to the English workshop. It considers the variables: expectations, additional resources, time availability, and preferences, a google forms questionnaire was used to develop this survey, the time required to fulfill the survey is 15 minutes.

Checking list of contextual observation: A checklist was created, based on the themes of the workshop, to identify the challenges and advancements of the participants during the educational process. This instrument was adapted according to the topics of A1 level learners, following the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. This instrument is used by means of a detailed and clear list of the actions to be evaluated, it was examined, and approved by 3 professors of the program pedagogy of national and foreign languages affiliated to the university Laica Eloy Alfaro de Manabí.

Post-Test: At the end of the workshop, participants have a final presentation to assess their English language level as a result of the learning process, to evaluate the impact and effectiveness of the teaching and learning within the educational intervention, making a contrast among the Pre-Test and the final presentation to notice the advancements. This instrument was prepared and evaluated by the workshop teachers, the presentation lasted 10 minutes per person and was used within the classroom where the classes were taught.

3.2. Process

This research process consisted of the following stages:

Stage 1: In this stage, the participants were selected, adults between 18 and 74 years old. This selection was based on their entrepreneurship, since this project was addressed to people who are part of the tourism sector of Manta.

Stage 2: A survey was developed to know about the expectations of the entrepreneurship, because it is important to consider what the participants want and the interests that they have concerning of the workshop.

Stage 3: In this stage, the entrepreneurs responded some questions to assess what they already know about English basic topics, as a way to get an idea what information the participants need to learn in classes.

Stage 4: During the teaching-learning process was necessary to measure the advancements of the entrepreneurs, for that reason, according to the topics an observation checking list was created to evaluate the progress of the participants, within this check list were the most basic and important topics of the A1 English level.

Stage 5: The last stage there was a final presentation, that is consider as a Post Test, this presentation was very important, since in this part the entrepreneurs demonstrated what they learned during all this time. This presentation was a contrast with the Pre Test, because in this part the participants answered the same questions than in the Pre Test, with the difference that in this occasion was orally to see how they have improve their speaking skill, in addition to this interrogations, they gave an explanation of their entrepreneurship, considering descriptions about what they do or sell, prices, and elaboration of the products.

3.3. Educational intervention:

This project had an educational intervention that lasted six months divide in two stages, the first one was from November until January, 32 classes were developed by using of the communicative approach, where vocabulary, content and grammatical structures were consolidated, each class lasted 2 hours, and each week a specific topic was covered, where practice and the corresponding feedback were given; and the second stage was from May until

July, in this period of time, 36 classes were taught applying the ECRIF framework to refine the oral expression of the entrepreneurs, the classes were given 3 days per week, two hours each class. This project was conformed by 2 teachers and 20 entrepreneurs. Both entrepreneurs and teachers played an active role in the process, and gaps, doubts and difficulties in the participants' English learning process were identified. For this reason, classes were offered from a basic level covering core and specific topics, specifically designed to meet the participants' work needs using English.

The conducted connection between the two stages in the workshop, where the ECRIF method was selectively applied to the second stage, serves as a crucial experiment to assess the impact of this framework on the development of classes aimed at enhancing the communication skills of the trainees. The deliberate exclusion of ECRIF in the first stage creates a controlled environment for evaluating the effectiveness of this teaching methodology. This approach not only offers valuable insights into the potential positive impact of ECRIF on communication skill development but also underscores the importance of methodological choices in shaping the overall learning outcomes. The findings from this analysis will likely provide valuable information for educators and curriculum designers seeking to optimize language teaching methodologies for the improvement of students' communication abilities.

The main objective is for the entrepreneurs to acquire the necessary knowledge to develop their communicative competence in English, which is why the workshop is divided into two stages.

The first stage focuses on consolidating content, vocabulary, and grammatical structures through the communicative method. Since the participants are adults accustomed to a behaviorist approach based on direct transmission and quantified measurement of learning, it is challenging to change the mindset or processes that they perceive as more effective. A diagnostic test was used first, which revealed that most of the entrepreneurs had no prior knowledge of the language.

The second stage focuses exclusively on the application of the ECRIF framework. Once the participants have acquired prior knowledge, this framework is used to apply this knowledge in practical situations, strengthening pronunciation and speaking skills. As a pedagogical model, ECRIF focuses on the specific needs of the learners and serves as a guide for curricular adaptations.

At the end of the second stage of the workshop, a post-test was conducted to evaluate the progress and improvements in the oral skills of the entrepreneurs. A before and after evaluation was conducted from the pre-test to the final presentation (post-test), using the oral presentation as the evaluation method. This approach allows us to determine the effectiveness of combining the communicative method for knowledge acquisition with the ECRIF framework for oral skills development.

4. Results

The results presentation follows the other of the research questions appearing in the introduction section.

4.1 In answer to the question: *What are the entrepreneurs' expectations for the workshop in EFL?*

The graphic 1 shows the participants' need for learning in EFL.

Graphic 1: Participants expectations for learning in the workshop

According to the graphic, the 89% of respondents that they would like to improve their communicative and oral expression. The 11% of the participants declared that they prefer to improve vocabulary.

4.1.1. In addition, other of the participants' expectations is to access to didactic material in English language.

Graphic 2: Participants' access to didactic material in EFL

4.2. In answer to the question 2. What is the previous English language level of the entrepreneurs at the beginning of the workshop?

The table 1 shows the results of the participants' previous knowledge in English language.

Table 1: Participants previous English language knowledge

N°	Topics assessed	Knowledge percentage
1	Names and surnames	50%
2	Age	30%
3	Professions	40%
4	Address & directions	10%
5	Frequency adverbs.	10%
6	Personal adjectives.	25%
7	Communication for promotion of products	10%
8	Numbers & prices	20%
9	Welcome the customers	40%
10	Close the business Farewells.	35%
11	American quantity system	25%
12	Location description	20%
13	English for sales	15%
Total		27,69%

Source: pretest of English previous knowledge.

It is observed that the entrepreneurs have a 27.69% command of the fundamental aspects of English, as well as the content and vocabulary related to their businesses or areas of work. The information was used to design the educational intervention.

4.3. In answer to the question 3. What topics of educational intervention in English language were the most difficult to learn for the participants during the execution of the educational intervention?

The table two shows the results of the contextual observations.

Table 2: Participants progress and difficulties in English classes.

Topics of educational intervention	Participants achievement				Observation
	100-75%	74-51%	50-26%	25-0%	
1. Use of INTRODUCE MYSELF	X				The students did not have difficulty using the mentioned topic.
2. Use of GREETINGS AND FAREWELLS	X				Students did not have difficulty using greetings and farewells.
3. Use of SPELLING		X			The students had difficulty using or applying the spelling of the different words presented.
4. Use of FOOD AND DRINKS vocabulary	X				The students had no difficulty using the topic of beverages and food.
5. Use of COUNTABLES AND UNCOUNTABLES NOUNS			X		The students encountered numerous challenges when attempting to utilize and apply the aforementioned topic.
6. Use of ADJECTIVES		X			The students encountered difficulties in applying the subject matter.
7. Use of PROFESSIONS AND OCCUPATIONS	X				The students did not encounter any challenges in utilizing the professions.
8. Use of SELLING AND BUYING vocabulary			X		The students experienced difficulties with the topic as they believed it to be overly complex.

Source: Contextual observations

The topics with the greatest learning difficulty were observed in the entrepreneurs are 5. Use of countable and uncountable nouns, and 8. use of selling and buying vocabulary.

4.4. In answer to the question 4. What is the achievement of the participants in English language grammar after part 1 of workshops?

The table three shows the achievement of the participants.

Table 3: Participants' achievement in EFL grammar after educational intervention

N°	Items	Grammar
1	Names and surnames	95%
2	Age	85%
3	Professions	100%
4	Address & directions	60%
5	Frequency adverbs.	70%
6	Personal adjectives.	80%
7	Communication for promotion of products	75%
8	Numbers & prices	85%
9	Welcome the customers	85%
10	Close the business Farewells.	85%
11	American quantity system	80%
12	Location description	75%
13	English for sales	70%
Total		76.54%

Source: Pos-test part 1

A significant change is observed at the end of the workshop, reaching a knowledge level of 76.54%. This represents an improvement of 48.85%, which marks the difference between their starting point and the state at the end of the first stage.

4.5. In answer to the question 5. What are the changes and improvements in the entrepreneurs' linguistic skills after the educational intervention?

The table four shows the improvements of the entrepreneurs.

Table 4: Participants' achievement in EFL speaking skills after educational intervention.

N°	Items	Speaking skill results
1	Names and surnames	100%
2	Age	95%
3	Professions	100%
4	Address & directions	85%
5	Frequency adverbs.	90%
6	Personal adjectives.	95%

7	Communication for promotion of products	90%
8	Numbers & prices	95%
9	Welcome the customers	95%
10	Close the business Farewells.	95%
11	American quantity system	90%
12	Location description	90%
13	English for sales	95%
Total		89.23%

Source: Post test part 2

The results show a significant progress through the application of the ECRIF framework as a method to enhance and improve the oral skills of the entrepreneurs. A final percentage of 89.23% was achieved in speaking skills, highlighting the relevance of vocabulary and content related to their field of work to strengthen their communicative competence.

5. Discussion

Based on the literature review and the field work of this research, authors affirm that, results ratify the position of Caiza (2021) and Briones (2022) when they share the idea practical application of the ECRIF framework along with Communicative method in the Ecuadorian classroom is relevant for improving the learners' speaking skills in English.-Thus, the use of ECRIF in this research with entrepreneurs showed significantly improve levels of speaking proficiency by encouraging the spontaneous and accurate expression and use of the language in both practice, teacher-direction, and learner' s production-initiated activities. In addition, teaching adult learners can be very rewarding, but also very difficult, as mentioned by Malik & Khaliq (2017) ratify that adults have special needs and requirement as learners, that is why in this research with adult entrepreneurs, these same demonstrated a slightly higher percentage in the use of the communicative method, and not with the ECRIF, the researchers can affirm that this is due to the learning style of older adults.

Finally, Knowles (1984) labels adult learners with six fundamental characteristics that they do not share with younger learners, these are (1) Adult learning is self-directed, (2) Adult learning uses knowledge and life experiences, (3) Adult learning is goal-oriented, (4) Adult learning is relevance-oriented, (5) Adult learning emphasizes practicality, and (6) Adult learning fosters collaboration. Cozma (2015) in the same way states that they are more mature and possess more experience than younger learners, although this could be both beneficial and problematic, although teachers need to supply them with reasons why each aspect of what they train is important.

The evidence presented shows that a combination of methodologies as communicative method and ECRIF framework had a positive impact on the teaching-learning process during the English workshops in groups of entrepreneurs. This is clearly reflected in the excellent results obtained by the entrepreneurs at the end of the educational intervention. Thus, using the communicative method participants pasted from 27.69% in pre-test to 76.54% (+48.85%) in post-test. Using the ECRIF participants reported 48.08% to 89.23% (+41.15) at the end. In addition, the direct adaptation of the lessons to the business environment, with an authentic and real-life approach, enabled the adult entrepreneurs to express themselves in English confidently and effectively.

For future educational interventions is recommended to incorporate specific approaches, content, and vocabulary related to entrepreneurs' products and business, facilitating effective communication with people who speaks English language, and strengthening their connection in the international market.

6. Conclusion

Based on the contrast of the analyzed literature and the empirical research, the authors declare 100% achievement of the proposed aims: to transfer the communicative competence in the English language to the entrepreneurs of Manta. By comparing the effectiveness of teaching based on the communicative approach and the use of ECRIF, it was concluded that the combination of both models promotes higher results in language transference. This integration significantly facilitates the teaching-learning process, allowing students to acquire content knowledge, vocabulary, and grammatical structures in English language, meanwhile improving their speaking skills. This study shows that by the end of the workshop, the entrepreneurs had made an impressive 89.23% progress. In contrast, at the beginning of the program, they had only 27.69% proficiency in the basics. The synergy between the two approaches resulted in a 61.54% improvement in content mastery and communicative competence in English as a foreign language. This result underscores the effectiveness of strategically combining different teaching methods and demonstrates that the synergy between the communicative method and ECRIF. The weakness of this research lies in the limited number of participants during the 6 months of the English workshop, for this reason the results obtained cannot be generalized, since it is necessary to carry out this process at least 3 more times and for a longer period of time to generate a theory. For this reason, other researchers are invited to carry out new investigations in the following line of research: communicative development in the foreign language of entrepreneurs in Manabí. It is hoped that this work will contribute to the socio-economic development of this important sector in Ecuador.

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